

HARMONY IN INNOVATION: NAVIGATING GLOBAL BUSINESS LANDSCAPES THROUGH EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES AND DYNAMIC MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES

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Abstract

The concept of Harmony in Innovation is a multifaceted approach that emphasizes the coordination of various elements within organizations to foster creativity, collaboration, and successful innovation processes. This holistic development process places a strong emphasis on the well-being of individuals, organizations, and the environment, aligning with the principles of sustainable growth and responsible business practices. By orchestrating the key levers of innovation, such as communication, collaboration, leadership, and technology, businesses can navigate the complexities of the global business landscape with agility and resilience. Emerging technologies play a crucial role in this paradigm, offering new opportunities for organizations to enhance operational efficiencies, drive growth, and create sustainable competitive advantages. Dynamic management strategies complement these technological advancements by enabling organizations to adapt swiftly to change, foster a culture of creativity, and capitalize on emerging opportunities. Through the harmonious integration of emerging technologies and dynamic management strategies, businesses can position themselves at the forefront of innovation, driving growth, fostering resilience, and shaping a prosperous future in the ever-evolving global business environment.

Keywords: Harmony, Mandala, Dynamic, Learning, Digital, Sustainable.

1. Introduction:

In the current knowledge era, companies compete by leveraging intangible resources such as technologies, innovations, employee abilities, and relationships with external partners (Mohapatra, S., Jena, S. K., Mitra, A., & Tiwari, A. K., 2019; Mollah, M. A. S., & Rouf, M. A., 2022). The concept of intellectual capital (IC) has gained significant attention among academics due to its impact on a country's competitiveness and success. Intangible assets, including intellectual capital, are increasingly recognized as strategic assets that contribute to a company's value and competitive advantages as we are in a VUCA world (Ni, Y., Cheng, Y. R., & Huang, P., 2020; Oppong, G. K., & Pattanayak, J. K., 2019; Pedro, E., Alves, H., & Leitão, J. (2018)). The VUCA world concept encapsulates the challenges posed by volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity in today's rapidly changing environment. Volatility refers to the speed of change, uncertainty relates to the predictability of the future, complexity involves the multitude of interconnected factors, and ambiguity signifies a lack of clarity in interpreting situations. These elements collectively make the world difficult to understand and navigate, requiring individuals and organizations to adapt, innovate, and

think strategically to thrive in such an environment (Nate Bennett and G. James Lemoine ,2014).

It serves as a framework for understanding and addressing the complexities and uncertainties present in the modern global landscape. The VUCA world demands adaptability, continuous learning, agility, and the ability to anticipate and respond to change effectively to succeed (Mishra, 2022). In essence, the VUCA world challenges traditional linear thinking, encourages flexibility, openness to change, critical thinking, diverse perspectives, and proactive problem-solving. It emphasizes the importance of developing a mindset that embraces uncertainty and values collaboration to navigate the complexities of today's dynamic world effectively (Goodwin, 2018: Mishra, Nepal A., P. S. Aithal, 2022: Snowden, 2019).

2. Statement of Problems:

The relationship between innovation and international business is crucial for companies seeking to compete globally. Innovation drives growth and sustains organizations in the face of marketplace fluctuations. Companies like Apple and Stanley Black & Decker are recognized as high-leverage innovators, excelling in innovation across different periods. Innovation in international business involves seeking new ideas both domestically and abroad to enhance competitiveness globally. Businesses investing in research and development can create new products and services, differentiating themselves from competitors and entering new markets. Technology and innovation have transformed communication, supply chain management, and business models in international business, offering new opportunities for growth and expansion. However, challenges such as cybercrime and regulatory compliance across different countries must be addressed to ensure sustainable growth and competitiveness. Innovation is a critical aspect of business across all industries, driving companies to constantly seek new ways to innovate and solve problems with fresh solutions. It is essential for businesses to understand the innovation process thoroughly and encourage creativity in the workplace to stay competitive in today's global market.

3. Objectives:

The paper aims to provide insights into how innovation, emerging technologies, and dynamic management strategies intersect in navigating global business landscapes effectively.

4. Status and Analysis

4.1 Navigating Global Business:

This notion of vuca is particularly relevant in the context of technological transformation, where organizations are constantly evolving to adapt to new technologies and remain competitive. The shift towards digital systems requires businesses to restructure operations, enhance customer interactions, and develop real-time insights, highlighting the transformative power of technology in modern society Goodwin, 2018: Mishra, Nepal A., P. S. Aithal, 2022: Snowden, 2019. In the context of digital transformation, leadership plays a crucial role in driving change and inspiring organizations to embrace technological advancements. However, it is essential to note that in digital transformation, leadership alone is not sufficient, as research and innovation also hold significant influence and capacity in

shaping the trajectory of technological evolution. Research and innovation contribute to the development of new technologies, processes, and strategies that are essential for successful digital transformations, highlighting their pivotal role(Ly B.2023) may give inference to call research and innovation is the real leader whose leadership in navigating the complexities of technological change.

According to Michel Dell, 85% of jobs that will exist in 2030 have not been invented yet, highlighting the uncertainty surrounding the future landscape of work in terms of education and required skill sets(Dell, M. (2017, July 15). In contrast, Forbes predicts that 75% of companies will disappear from their current spaces by 2025, indicating a significant level of disruption and transformation expected in the business world. Additionally, it is noteworthy that 50% of future companies have not even begun their operations yet, underscoring the dynamic and evolving nature of industries as they navigate towards the future. These insights collectively emphasize the need for adaptability, innovation, and preparedness for the forthcoming changes in the job market and business environment.

4.2 Emerging Technologies: Anticipated Transformations in the New Decade

Some examples of emerging technologies in global business landscapes include Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), which revolutionize automation, decision-making, and customer engagement. Blockchain technology enhances security and trust in transactions, while Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) create immersive experiences for customers and training purposes. Predictive analytics utilizes data mining and machine learning to forecast trends and optimize operations. The Internet of Behaviors (IoB) combines technology, data analytics, and behavioral science to understand user behavior, improving customer experiences and personalizing services. These technologies are reshaping business operations, customer interactions, and competitiveness in a rapidly evolving global market, offering opportunities for innovation, efficiency improvements, and strategic positioning.

News are the best teachers as given example

Robert CEO: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8BQEyQ2-awc>

Devin, the first AI software engineer: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fjHtjT7GO1c>

<https://www.wionews.com/science/scientists-develop-recyclable-water-batteries-that-never-explode-698295>

<https://scitechdaily.com/supercomputers-crack-the-code-of-super-diamond-synthesis/>

<https://www.wionews.com/science/scientists-develop-recyclable-water-batteries-that-never-explode-698295>

The first source discusses an AI robot 'CEO,' while the second one introduces Devin as the first AI software engineer. The third source highlights the development of recyclable 'water batteries' that do not explode and so on.

4.3 Anticipated Transformations in the New Decade:

As Forrester. (2024, March 23) predicts the possibilities of change are as follow:

- The dawn of a new decade heralds a wave of transformative changes that are poised to reshape our world in ways both fascinating and unsettling. Here are some intriguing and, at times, disquieting predictions that are likely to materialize in the coming years:

- ❑ **Disappearance of Auto Repair Shops:**
Traditional auto repair shops may fade into obscurity as electric cars with minimal parts and lifetime guarantees dominate the automotive landscape.
- ❑ **Rise of Electric Cars and Regional Repair Centers:**
Electric cars, boasting a mere 20 parts compared to 20,000 in petrol/diesel engines, will revolutionize transportation. Faulty electric motors will be swiftly repaired by robots at regional centers.
- ❑ **Efficient Electric Motor Replacement:**
Malfunctioning electric motors can be swiftly replaced at specialized centers while you enjoy a cup of coffee, akin to a car wash experience.
- ❑ **Transition Away from Petrol Pumps:**
The era of petrol pumps will wane as street corners feature electricity dispensing meters and companies establish electrical recharging stations.
- ❑ **Shift Towards Renewable Energy:**
Homes will increasingly generate and store electrical energy, selling excess power back to the grid and transforming the energy landscape.
- ❑ **Disruption in Traditional Industries:**
The advent of artificial intelligence, autonomous vehicles, and advanced technologies will disrupt traditional industries, leading to significant transformations in various sectors.
- ❑ **Technological Advancements in Healthcare:**
Innovations like the Tricorder X promise revolutionary advancements in healthcare, enabling rapid disease diagnosis through smartphone-compatible devices.
- ❑ **Environmental Impact:**
The widespread adoption of electric cars and renewable energy sources will lead to cleaner air, reduced noise pollution, and a significant decline in fossil fuel consumption.

Fig. 1: Digital Universe in Web 3.0

[Digital Transformation (DT) = Sustainable Development (SD)]

The main focus of the intellectual society should be on balancing the Digital Transformation with sustainable Development and the business grow in between that as the integration of Business Chemistry principles with sustainable development practices and digital

transformation in mandala art therapy showcases diverse applications of these concepts across business relationships, environmental sustainability, and mental health interventions.

As we stand on the cusp of unprecedented technological advancements and societal shifts, the future promises a landscape that is both exhilarating and challenging. Embracing these changes with foresight and adaptability will be key as we navigate the uncharted territories that lie ahead. The new decade beckons with opportunities for innovation, progress, and transformation beyond our current imagination. Embracing Web 3.0 empowers businesses to explore new ways of interaction, nurture innovations, establish novel business relationships, and adapt to a future where ownership, incentives, and community models are redefined to meet the demands of a rapidly evolving digital economy. As your own universe is coming soon mandala universe (Ananda, N., Kobayashi, S., Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S., 2023).

4.4 Dynamic Management Strategies:

Dynamic management strategies play a crucial role in helping businesses navigate global landscapes by enabling them to adapt to changing scenarios, minimize operational threats, and seize new opportunities. These strategies offer a framework that allows leaders to respond appropriately to shifting demands, build flexibility and innovation into decision-making processes, and actively adapt to real-time situations. By embracing dynamic management strategies, organizations can enhance their awareness of internal and external influences, better prepare to deal with challenges, and increase their likelihood of achieving key goals such as penetrating new markets, increasing market share, or forming strategic partnerships. In contrast, static business strategies tend to be reactive, leading to limitations, missed opportunities, and a lack of preparedness for change, which can result in disruption and confusion. Dynamic management strategies, rooted in concepts like dynamic capability theory, emphasize the importance of integrating, building, and reconfiguring internal and external competencies to address rapidly changing environments. This approach allows companies to adjust core competencies, modify competitive positions, enhance long-term competitive advantage, and stimulate corporate agility, ultimately leading to strategic resilience and value creation.

These strategies focus on building a culture of learning, adaptability, and cross-cultural understanding within organizations, enabling them to effectively navigate the complexities of the global business landscape shown in figure 2.

4.5. Harmony in Innovation:

NEED=LEAD

- Create a Pipeline of promising ideas
- Pilot experimentation and validation
- Commercialization launch and ram up through Entrepreneurship
- Improvement cycle
- Create Blue Ocean

Fig. 2: Harmony in Innovation

Several innovation has been highlighted by Mishra(2024) as it is multiple use of single thing. Washing machine uses for making *Lassi*. Harmony in innovation refers to the cohesive integration of various elements within an organization to foster creativity, collaboration, and successful innovation processes. It involves aligning different aspects such as communication, cooperation, leadership, culture, and technology to create a synergistic environment that nurtures innovation and drives growth. Achieving harmony in innovation requires a holistic approach that considers the well-being of individuals, organizations, and the environment, emphasizing a balance between diverse forces and values. By orchestrating these key levers of innovation in a coordinated manner, businesses can enhance their competitive edge, improve customer experiences, and adapt to the dynamic demands of the modern business landscape. Ultimately, harmony in innovation enables organizations to navigate challenges, capitalize on opportunities, and create sustainable value for stakeholders while fostering a culture of continuous improvement and adaptability.

4.6 Path of Educational Institutions:

Education is transitioning to digital storage, moving away from traditional memorization. A coupon system is emerging, allowing on-demand education through call centers. This system is evolving to resemble a health card, where educational needs are met instantly with an educational card. Similar to purchasing with a card, educational packages can be acquired based on requirements. Educational institutions may transform into research centers, akin to cyber cafes dispensing documents based on payment, or hospitals providing services based on fees. The shift aims to preserve the educational institution's integrity by emphasizing research over transactional services (Mishra, 2022). So the proposed path will be sustainable academic operation path.

Fig. 3: Path of Educational Institutions for Future (Mishra & Nepal, 2022)

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, achieving harmony in innovation amidst the evolving global business landscapes requires a strategic blend of emerging technologies and dynamic management strategies. The fusion of cutting-edge technologies like artificial intelligence, blockchain,

Internet of Behaviours, and data analytics with agile and adaptive management approaches is essential for organizations to thrive in today's competitive environment. By embracing innovation and leveraging these technologies, businesses can enhance operational efficiencies, drive growth, and create sustainable competitive advantages. Moreover, the ability to navigate the complexities of global markets, regulatory environments, and consumer preferences through a harmonious integration of technology and management strategies is paramount for long-term success as harmony in innovation through proposed futuristic academic operation. As businesses continue to evolve in the digital age, those that proactively embrace innovation, foster a culture of creativity, and adapt swiftly to change will emerge as leaders in their respective industries. By fostering harmony between innovation and management, organizations can position themselves at the forefront of the ever-changing global business landscape, driving growth, fostering resilience, and shaping a prosperous future.

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A STUDY ON EFFECT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ADVERTISEMENTS ON CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTIONS

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Abstract

The goal of this research paper's development was to gain a thorough understanding of the mechanisms, characteristics, and other aspects of social media advertisements across all social media platforms, as well as how these elements are influencing potential customers' buying behaviour or, more precisely, their intention to make a purchase. The approach is a hybrid of exploratory research design and causal research design. The results of the replies to the questionnaire were interesting since they showed that some aspects of social media adverts had a greater influence on consumers' purchase intentions than others. Customers favoured some features of the adverts in their feeds over other features. Any party that is interested will gain valuable knowledge from the study of their implications. The demographics of the respondents were restricted to a specific number, so a larger sample size would make more sense in the future. A potential restriction is that the developed hypothesis' applicability may change depending on the situation. Organisations wishing to understand their customer base's preferences in the social media space can use the practical implications of this study as a guide, potentially helping them to increase their brand equity.

Keywords— Advertisements, Consumer Behaviour, Marketing, Social Media

Introduction

The value proposition of 21st-century organisations' products is being filtered through digital platforms rather than traditional methods and platforms to focus on global development, monitor market trends, and gain the full benefits of new technology. Like other economic sectors, advertising is being taken advantage of by these digital platforms. In connection with this, social media platforms make up most of these digital platforms. Today, businesses use platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Gmail, and Outlook to advertise to and promote their target audiences of consumers. These platforms include the instruments and tools that help advertisers appeal to, comprehend, influence, and fully grasp the tastes, preferences, and inclinations of their target audience. In contrast to traditional advertising, which places print and broadcast media in the space and minds of the consumer, this new generation of internet advertising encourages people to visit them. Pop-up advertisements, HTML ads, text-template ads, GIF ads, and interstitial advertisements are a few of the techniques and tools used in the world of Internet advertising. A feature known as "Dark Posts" is used by several social media platforms, like Facebook and Instagram, to allow advertisers to present their

online adverts to their target audiences as sponsored material, which subsequently occasionally appears in their feed or timeline. Then, these various tool and mechanism spectrums are evaluated based on factors such as data traffic, frequency on websites, clicks per ad, and clicks per website. This study examines the effectiveness of social media advertising and how it differs from other forms of consumer influence, such as broadcasting and print media.

Review of Literature

Kaplan, Andreas & Haenlein, Michael. (2010)¹ The writers have discussed the challenges of social media and the opportunities put forward with the use of social media.

Muntinga, Daan, Moorman, Marjolein, & Smit, Edith. (2011)² The authors have discussed the use of social media on brands, and how the use impacts the brands.

Research Methodology

This work combines an exploratory and causal research approach to test and identify a trend, namely the impact of social media marketing on purchase intention. Information is gathered from both primary and secondary sources.

Data Interpretation & Analysis

This section of the study focuses on the data gathered, its interpretation from multiple angles, its implications that relate to the questions raised by the study, and any potential hypotheses for those concerns. There were 91 responses altogether, and a thorough analysis is provided below. –

How much time approx. do you spend on social media platforms?

90 responses

64.4% of the respondents reportedly spent 1-3 hours on social media. The next larger portion went to those who used it for 4-6 hours, which was approximately 25.6%. Only 4.4% and 3.3%, respectively, of users used it for 7-9 and 10 hours. In this case, 0 hours corresponds to less than an hour of usage, hence only 2 respondents (2.2%) chose it.

Implications:

Although social media platforms have seen a rise, most users spend between 13 and 4-6 hours per day on them, indicating a moderate level of usage.

How often do you resort to social media platforms, when you have confusion regarding purchasing a product?

90 responses

Despite the increase of social media sites, most users only spend 13 to 4–6 hours per day using them, which indicates a modest level of consumption. Q2.

Implication: - Since 23.4% of individuals are unlikely to use SMP (17.8% + 5.6%), this statistic shows that 76.6% of people are more likely than not to use SMP when they are unsure about purchasing a product.

On your social media feed, you like ads that are rich in text form.

90 responses

On the contrast, 31.1% decided to agree, while roughly 26.7% chose to stay neutral. About 33.3% chose not to agree. Around 6.7% of respondents strongly agreed, while 2.2% strongly disagreed.

Implications: - This indicates that text types in social media advertisements are liked and disliked by the population or samples almost equally. (SDA plus DA = 35.7% / SDA plus A = 38%) So, in order to be entertaining, a social media advertisement should contain a mix of text and image formats.

Social media ads which allow you to scroll through/view the product from different angles, engage you.

90 responses

Implication: By boosting interactivity, social media ads with 360-degree views can affect consumers' desire to buy.

Pop up ads on your feed, (ads which literally pop up) entice/attract you.
90 responses

Implication: Pop-up adverts, a type of online advertising, generally have a negative effect on consumers' intentions to make a purchase.

On your social media feed, you don't mind the quantity of info on the ad as long as its entertaining/eye-catching.
90 responses

Implication: For the most part, entertainment in a social media advertisement is more significant than information itself.

Social media ads in the form of surveys, increase your engagement towards it.
90 responses

Implication: Surveys in social media ads increase involvement and affect purchasing decisions, even though some people find them time-consuming.

On your social media feed, ads that have high resolution and vibrant pictures attract you.
90 responses

Implication: Images and pixels with high contrast and resolution increase aesthetic value and have a significant impact on consumer decisions.

What information do you look for the most amongst ads in your social media feed?

90 responses

Implication: Information, particularly information on the features of a product, has a significant impact on consumers' purchasing decisions.

You always get the correct/required amount of information from the social media ads, on your feed.

90 responses

Implication: Now, SMP and advertisements are not providing users with the correct and necessary information about goods and services.

7. Conclusion

The conclusions drawn from the data analysis and insights about the earlier-formed prospective hypothesis will be presented in this section of the article. According to the first hypothesis (H1.1 - Information Feature of SM Ads), the information contained in a social media advertisement has the greatest impact on consumers' purchasing decisions. Even though SMP doesn't give correct information about the advertisement, it nevertheless has the maximum impact. The most significant influence on purchasing behaviour is information presented as product features. The second hypothesis was equally correct and led to the conclusion that (H1.2 - Entertainment Feature) - although some individuals prefer rich text forms in their advertisements, high resolution and bright photos, GIFs, etc. provide higher aesthetic value and thus affect consumer behaviour. Even when there is little information available, a social media advertisement's entertainment component might affect consumer behaviour. Although surveys are out of date, it was observed that the third hypothesis (H 1.3 - Interactive feature) enhances interactivity, which in turn influences consumer buying behaviour. Ads with 360-degree views and angles also had higher levels of involvement. A balance in terms of interactivity must be maintained because consumers dislike SM advertisements with too many interfaces. Consumers thought that product features in an SM

ad boosted confidence in it, supporting the final hypothesis of the first model (H1.4 - credibility feature). Additionally, they thought that SM ads were more trustworthy than mass media ones. Additionally, because social media ads' credibility is so important, even those that meet customer needs but lack credibility are ignored. H2.1 (EWOM) - comments, posts, etc. affect buying behaviour as consumers perceived a shift in their attitude after viewing them - was also seen to be true based on the data. Additionally, user reviews from across these platforms played a role in influencing purchasing decisions. Even though EWOM had an impact on the purchasing process, most consumers did not actively participate. They were additionally persuaded to test new items by EWOM. H2.2 (Online communities) - Even though many respondents did not participate in online communities (such as social media sites), their content had a minimal impact on them. H2.3 (Internet advertisements) GIFs and high-resolution images used in social media ads had the most impact on consumers' purchasing decisions, while pop-up ads barely had any effect. Last but not least, despite consumers' perceptions that social media advertising was more effective and reputable than mass media commercials, some respondents felt that these ads also created complications, such as many ads, phoney ads, scams, excessive interfaces, etc. As a result, every hypothesis formed is satisfied by this paper.

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ASSESSING HUMAN RESOURCE ACCOUNTING: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract

As a vital instrument for evaluating the worth of human capital and making strategic decisions, human resource accounting (HRA) has gained popularity. From conceptual inception to modern methodologies, this paper offers a thorough analysis of the development of HRA. Using scholarly contributions as a guide, the study traces the historical evolution of HRA. It is becoming increasingly important in organizational decision-making, especially when it comes to matching overall business goals with human resource initiatives. The study emphasizes how transparent valuation techniques are essential for accurately assessing human capital's worth and enabling equitable resource distribution and pay. The paper concludes by addressing the changing difficulties that businesses have in valuing and reporting human capital and acknowledging the continued work of scholars to improve HRA approaches.

Keywords: Decision-Making, Human Resource Accounting and Human Capital

Introduction:

People are valuable financially to businesses because they possess skills and expertise. Within the company, human resources are viewed as intangible assets, often known as intellectual capital (IC) or human capital (HC). Human resources (HR) can be invested in, and returns can be calculated. The HC theory for the development of economic value views HR's competencies, knowledge, and abilities as an output rather than an input (Abhayawansa and Abeysekera, 2008). There are several ways to evaluate an HR department's success within a company, but not many that take into account the financial input and output. HR accounting assesses human resources based on the profit and loss statement.

The value of management growth, human resource capital, and the appreciation of management accounting can all be ascertained via the application of human resource accounting (HRA). According to Turner (1996), there was another aspect of employee valuation that was acknowledged as a liability, along with related expenditures and perks like pay and employee turnover. Huge amounts of work are done there and have gained recognition. According to Euske and Osterhoudt (1987), army troops are also subject to this accounting principle. The administration uses HRA as a tool to make decisions about both

organizational objectives and human resources. Decision-making was demonstrated to be based on HRA (Hendricks, 1976). It is one of the evaluation procedures for any company's human resources. As time went on, several HRA techniques were put forth, and when they were compared to other valuation techniques, it was discovered that their asset composition was drastically different (Theeke, 2005). This document provides an overview of human resource accounting along with a brief description of its techniques.

The consumers employed several suggested ways based on the information they needed (Aljamaan, 2017). Because human resource assets are not like other assets that have all the rights granted to them by the firm, financial reporters and accountants do not embrace HRA (Cherian and Farouq, 2013). In terms of reporting, the main goal is to comprehend the importance of HR in relation to the critical elements required for corporate success. According to a forthcoming study, the financial evaluation of human capital yields a variety of benefits (Fulmer and Ployhart, 2014). Techniques used to quantify the value of HR aid in decision-making and eventually serve as the foundation for a company's competitive advantage. Diversity and a wide scope are revealed in the written articles by all the studies on human capital, intellectual capital, and HRA conducted in previous years (Theeke and Mitchell, 2008). Numerous economists and scholars have examined and interpreted the word HRA in various contexts.

Literature Review:

As noted by Hull (1899), Sir William Petty originally introduced the idea of valuing human resources in 1691. He represents the nation's wealth source and the potential of workers with monetary worth. Since human talents are acquired at expense, Jean Baptiste argued in 1821 that they should be viewed as capital. This similar hypothesis was also advanced by Walter Bagehot, John Stuart Mill, Henry Sidgwick, and William Roscher (Kiker, 1966). According to Walsh (1935), William Farr (1853) taxed this human worth word in a different way.

An abstraction of capital commodities was first presented to humans by Theodor Wittstein in 1867. According to Kiker (1966), Johann H. Von Thunen first discussed labor productivity expenditures in 1875 as a component of the human capital analytical framework. People possess all the characteristics that demonstrate their status as a capital element, according to Irving Fisher in 1897 (Fisher, 1897). Around 1883, Ernst Engel defined the process by which humans were judged to be worth their cost of creation (Kiker, 1966). The 1930 study by Dublin and Alfred Lotka determined a person's monetary value in relation to their family. Remarkably, human talent has a cost and may also generate profit, according to the famous philosopher Adam Smith (1937), who is frequently cited as the founder of modern economics. Senior (1939) William Nassau came to the conclusion that while human talents and abilities require upkeep, they are considered capital because they yield future results. When measuring the value of human capital, Alfred Marshall talked about the implications in 1961 (Marshall, 1961). According to T.W. Schultz's statement in 1959, "the main stream of modern economics has bypassed undertaking any systematic analysis of human wealth" for the same reason. By appraising a company's human resources and tracking fluctuations in

their worth, Rensis Likert investigated the human resource accounting system (Likert, 1967). Measurement techniques for the cost of human resources were examined and presented by Brummet, Flamholtz, and Pyle. R.G. Barry Corporation devised a series of methods to distinguish between the asset and expense components of human resource expenditures and put the system of human resource accounting into place (Pyle, 1970). The unpurchased goodwill method and the adjusted present value method are the two workable approaches for the financial appraisal of human resources that Hermanson proposed (Hermanson, 1986). Working on human worth for organizations, William C. Pyle published his writings.

A human resource value model using discounted future pay was introduced by Lev and Schwartz in 1971. "The process of identifying and measuring data about human resources and communicating this information to interested parties" is how the American Accounting Association described human resource accounting in 1973 (Report of the Committee on Human Resource Accounting, 1973). The percentage of investment in human assets to total assets is known as "Human Asset Investment (HAI)," according to Cerullo (1974). Sincere work was carried out by various researchers for the analysis of human resources expenditures and income to propose different concepts.

A dynamic system model in HRA is depicted to analyze the share of contribution to profit by the labor force and collaborators (Gambling, 1976). Gradually, a measurement theory perspective model was developed to assess human value with defined constructs and criteria in an organizational environment (Grove et al., 1977). The costs incurred can be taken in the form of original costs, replacement costs, and opportunity costs (Spiceland and Zaunbrecher, 1976). In past decades, organizations have also used human resource accounting in the following ways: "1) through the development of systems of accounting for human resource costs and value, and 2) on a problem-oriented basis" (Flamholtz, 1974). The information obtained from the HRA system can be helpful in many fields; therefore, growth is required in the area. The development of HRA refers to two general approaches for measuring human assets: the first is outlay-based, and the second is inflow-oriented (Craft and Birnberg, 1976).

Methodology:

This study includes a comprehensive review of journals and papers on HRA. The provided qualitative study conducted a review of the literature using published articles from various databases. The goal of this study is to identify scholarly research on HRA. The value of human resources has been greatly influenced by the diverse ideas put forth by economists and researchers. Research papers were gathered from several databases in order to comprehend the topic's progressive scenario. Papers up until 2024 were chosen and grouped according to three time periods based on applicable material. Although the value of human resources was recognized in the seventeenth century, attempts at human capital accounting were attempted for the first time in the 1960s (James and Vijaya, 2009). The popularity of the motif has been gradually increasing, as seen in Figure 1. The table 1 given below represents the paper citations by the field authors.

Figure 1: Research at different time-frames

Source: Author’s own

Table 1: Authors and citations

Most Cited Author’s Names	Citation Numbers
Likert R. (1967)	6038
Senior N.W. (1836)	690
Lev, B. and Schwartz, A. (1971)	492
Schultz T.W. (1959)	459
Kiker B.F. (1966)	455

Source: Author’s own

Apart from the aforementioned discussion of human resource accounting, there are numerous different ideas discussed by researchers for the valuation of HR in Table 2. The first column represents the author names and the HR philosophies given by them in the respective second column.

Table 2 HR philosophies given by researchers on HRA.

Author’s Name	HR Philosophies
Roslender and Fincham, 2001	Self-accounting as a notion was came in existence in order to stimulate self-awareness of person’s participation in organisation
Flamholtz et al., 2002	Skandia Navigator model was developed to present a stabilized image of organizational resources like intellectual capital, financial capital etc. and considers this as a process of management for estimating the future value of capital resources
Flamholtz et al., 2004	A strategy was designed to make the firms understand the importance and execution of HRA; three steps need to be

	followed to achieve this aim
Chen and Lin, 2004	Four quadrants framework was given which establishes the relationship between employees' value and uniqueness of employees to deliver the competitive advantage of organization
Theeke, 2005	A new consideration of human resource reporting in financial statements as liability paradigm was discussed
Chaudhry and Roomi, 2010	A new remark added in HRA that growth of the organization and profit outcomes were found positively proportional to the human capital investments made by the firm
Steen et al., 2011	Including all the different perceptions about valuing and reporting HR reveals the link between HR, intellectual capital and goodwill of the organization
Avazzadehfath and Raiashekar, 2011	HRA information and decision-making relativeness was analysed in terms of profit-making and attracting investments. It can be concluded that obtained information is helpful for individuals' stock investments and the management decision-making process of the firm
Cherian and Farouq, 2013	It is found that implementation of HRA in firms costs high and also focuses on HRA technology adaptation process to assess the various types of intellectual property
Ganta and Geddam, 2014	HRA proven helpful to management and employees both; recognizing and averting labour turnover to former and upgrading performance and haggling power to later
Uysal, 2016	In HRA, Intangible assets and intellectual capital are the terms used to denote HR in balance sheet of a firm
Osinski et al., 2017	Analysis has been done to find out the applicable method to report intangible assets in public as well as private sectors.

Source: Author's own

Conclusion and Future Directions:

Each organization's most valuable asset is its people, and executives face a significant task in creating strategies that will keep them competitive. The HR department's effectiveness in analyzing employee value amply illustrates the need for this study. There are practically endless applications for the theory of intangible or human assets. Applying any of the

aforementioned HRA techniques can help organizations determine the true value of their workforce, providing a more comprehensive and clear picture of this. This study highlights the evolution and improvements in HRA over time, demonstrating the ongoing quest to understand the importance of HR and financial statement reporting. Accounting firms developed HRA as a tool for measuring HR performance. It provides accountants with a variety of approaches to address organizational performance requirements related to staffing.

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ANALYSIS OF DISTRIBUTION CHANNELS FOR FISH TRADE IN MARINE FISHERIES CONCERNING PALGHAR DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract:

India stands as the second-largest contributor to global fish production, making up 6.7% of the total output. The fisheries industry's economic significance is evidenced by its dominant position within agricultural exports, with fish and fish product exports alone accounting for a substantial value of ₹46,663 crores in the fiscal year 2019-20. A crucial facet of this study is the examination of the impact of these distribution channels on the different stakeholders engaged in the marine fisheries industry. The current study has been carried out to answer the various problems faced by the Fishermen and other stakeholders in marine fish distribution channels. By scrutinizing these issues, the study aims to unearth insights that can drive positive changes within the marine fisheries distribution channels.

Keywords: Marine Fish Distribution, Marine Fish Problems, Middlemen, Stakeholders.

Introduction:

The fisheries sector in India is acknowledged as a robust source of income, achieving remarkable double-digit compound annual growth of 10.87% starting from the fiscal year 2014-15. This growth stimulates the growth of related industries, offers an affordable and nutritious food source, and caters to the sustenance of a considerable segment of the economically disadvantaged populace. Given its multifaceted contributions, the fisheries sector occupies a pivotal role in India's socio-economic development. In the context of India, fishing represents a swiftly expanding industry that not only addresses the dietary needs of the vast population but also generates livelihoods and income for over 28 million individuals. Maharashtra State stands as one of India's prominent maritime regions, boasting a coastline stretching 720 kilometers across six maritime districts: Thane, Mumbai Suburban, Mumbai City, Raigad, Ratnagiri, and Sindhudurg. Exploitation extends to the continental shelf area up to 40 fathoms, encompassing 55,529 square kilometers (50% of the total continental shelf). Within these districts, there are 25 zones and 162 fish landing centers. The state's fish potential is estimated at 6.3 lakh tonnes, with current production reaching 71% of this potential according to the Maharashtra State Fisheries Department (2020). The marine sector dominates the state's fishery sector, divided into 25 zones. Marine fishery focuses on the exploitation of seawater or ocean resources. Maharashtra's marine harvest comprises approximately 49 commercially significant species, including Sardine, Non-Penaeid Prawns,

Bombay duck, Penaeid Prawns, Pomfret, Seer fishes, Black pomfret, Eles, Lobsters, and Mackerels, among others.

Literature review:

(Markad et al., 2019) The present study was applied to study the status of fish market in Hingoli region in terms of facilities, equipment, cold chain, market construction, cleanliness, hygiene, important species sold, facility pricing structures, women's associations and marketing systems. Research shows that none of the fish markets in Hingoli have proper cold and freezer storage, cleanliness, sanitary conditions and market construction. Most of the markets are built on the side of the open road in an unsanitary condition. The price structure at fish markets varies according to various factors, for example species, size, quality, season, etc. The study suggests that local administrations should initiate and implement some basic fish market facilities. Fisherman ought to be trained and prepared in hygienic fish processing and handling.

(Rahman et al., 2019) This research endeavor aimed to delve into the intricacies of marketing channels, associated costs, and the marketing margins pertaining to marine fish transactions involving various intermediaries at the fishing port of Banjarmasin, Indonesia. Notably, wholesalers emerged as key players, reaping profits that were 2-6 times greater than those earned by local traders or retailers. Interestingly, the marketing margin observed for fish sold outside the fishing port surpassed that within the port itself. This discrepancy was attributed to the additional costs incurred during handling and transportation. The study highlighted the need for strategic interventions, suggesting the establishment of ice plant facilities at the fishing port. Moreover, the study advocated for the utilization of data technology to attract potential investors or entrepreneurs, creating a focused hub for the fisheries industry.

(Vala et al., 2020) This study was conducted at fish markets in Himmatnagar, Sabakantaha and investigated the marketing system, marketing process and financial characteristics. This study has shown the market infrastructure, the current state of the market, the nature of costs and the factors affecting the market system. Numerous individuals were engaged with fish distribution and marketing system. Many fishermen were discovered working independently for fishing and selling. The study proposed setting up several ice-plants, cold-storerooms, modern wholesaling, and preservation facilities. Providing mechanical weighing gear and improving sanitation, sterile condition, seepage, washing facilities and enough sale places will improve the fish market structure.

Research methodology:

A descriptive research design is used in this study. This study is a cross-sectional study. The study is carried out in the Palghar maritime district of Maharashtra. The survey was conducted in six zones of Palghar districts, namely Dahanu, Pophran Dandi, Satpati, Kelwa, Bassein (Vasai), and Uttan.

Convenience Sampling method has been used for this study. It is a sampling method that allows for the randomization of sample selection. The calculated Sample Size is 150 Respondents. From each zone, 25 samples were collected.

Primary data was collected through the survey method from Intermediaries (Fishermen, Auctioneers, Wholesalers, Retailers and Vendors) using a structured questionnaire and the

secondary data for the study was collected from sources like Govt. reports, online publications, reputed journals, magazines, newspapers, books etc.

This research mainly focuses on analysing the distribution channels of marine Fish in the Palghar district of Maharashtra by identifying distribution channels and evaluating the price spread and efficiency of different distribution channels. The marketing efficiency is a measure of market performance, that focuses on reducing marketing costs without reducing output or results.

Results and discussion:

The network of auctioneers, wholesalers, retailers, vendors, and transporters is integral to the marine fish distribution channels, facilitating the journey of fish from fishermen to end consumers. The significant distribution channels that operate within Palghar for marine fish distribution have been identified and will be expounded upon in subsequent sections.

Major distribution channels

1. Fishermen--Auctioneers--Retailers--Consumers
2. Fishermen--Auctioneers--Vendors--Consumers
3. Fishermen--Wholesalers--Retailers--Consumers
4. Fishermen--Wholesalers--Vendors--Consumers
5. Fishermen--Auctioneers--Wholesalers--Retailers--Vendors--Consumers

Table 1: Distribution / Marketing efficiency of distribution channels

Particulars (Rs. /Kg.)	Overall average				
	Channel -1	Channel -2	Channel - 3	Channel - 4	Channel -5
Price Spread (Rs. /kg)	45.04	35.21	40.98	44.89	46.03
Fishermen share in consumer rupee (%)	78.86	83.94	78.98	81.62	79.89
Marketing Distribution efficiency	4.42	5.87	4.76	4.64	4.23

The above table shows that the Distribution / Marketing efficiency of distribution channels was good for channel 2 followed by channel 3. These two channels' price spread is less, and fishermen's share in consumer rupees percentage is higher than other channels. So, we can conclude that these two channels are very efficient.

Table No. 2: Mean of intensities of problems in different zones of Palghar district for distribution of marine fish

Zone	Mean of Intermediators' problems	Mean of Infrastructure problems	Mean of Cold Storage problems	Mean of Marketing problems	Mean of Transport problems
Dahanu	1.53	3.33	2.13	2.98	2.05
Pophran-Dandi	1.51	3.67	3.87	4.61	3.95
Satpati	1.41	1.78	1.37	2.13	1.96
Kelwa	3.76	2.06	2.32	2.43	1.89
Vasai	3.87	1.17	1.27	2.21	1.87
Uttan	1.53	1.45	1.23	1.68	1.82

The above table depicts different mean values of intensities of problems in different zones of the Palghar district of Maharashtra for the distribution of marine fish. The high mean value of a problem indicates that such a problem's intensity is high in that zone. Dahanu Zone faces significant challenges related to marketing problems and a lack of Infrastructure support from the local government. Pophran-Dandi, is very intensely affected by various problems such as Infrastructure, Cold Storage, Marketing and transport problems. Satpati and Uttan as such not affected by any severe problems. Kelva and Vasai zone has been highly affected by the Intermediators' problems. The intensities of the problems vary with respect to the zones of Palghar district. Based on the above information, we can interpret that the zones of Palghar district are not facing the same intensities of problems when it comes to marine fish distribution. Instead, they are facing different intensities of problems.

Conclusion and suggestions:

The above study concludes that the Fishermen have a high share of the consumer rupee in channels 2 and 3 and hence the marketing efficiency increases in the case of such distribution channels. There is a need to establish more community-owned storage facilities at small landing centres where fishermen can collectively store their catch for better control of fish quality. Also need to develop mobile auction platforms that allow auctioneers to reach a wider market, enabling buyers from distant locations to participate. Govt. should explore partnerships with transportation companies to negotiate bulk rates for fish transportation, reducing costs for wholesalers, retailers and vendors. Also Advocate for infrastructure improvements, including better storage facilities, more space, and improved hygiene practices within the marketplace.

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IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGICAL INVESTMENT ON SUSTAINABLE PERFORMANCES (ESG) OF INDIAN COMPANIES

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Abstract

The research investigates the impact of digital technology investment on sustainability goals within Indian companies. Employing a causal research design, the study examines the relationship between Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) scores and technological investment. Data from 200 companies listed on the Nifty index in India were analyzed, revealing significant positive associations between ESG scores and environmental, social, and governance factors. However, the study found that the impact of investment in digital technology on ESG scores was relatively small and statistically non-significant. This suggests that while environmental, social, and governance practices strongly contribute to organizational sustainability goals, the direct influence of digital technology investment on sustainability performance may be less pronounced. The findings underscore the importance for companies to prioritize efforts in improving ESG factors to enhance overall sustainability performance. Furthermore, the study highlights the need for future research to explore additional variables and synergistic relationships between technology investment and sustainability outcomes, providing valuable insights for strategic decision-making processes regarding investment priorities and resource allocation strategies in pursuit of sustainable business practices.

Keywords

- Digital Technology
- ESG Scores
- Innovation
- Sustainability
- Technological Investment

1. Introduction

In today's global business landscape, environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors are increasingly integrated, reflecting a shift towards sustainable practices. Businesses, especially in India, are facing pressing challenges concerning the environment, societal inequality, and corporate governance. Embracing digital technology for sustainability becomes imperative in such a scenario. This study aims to explore the dynamics of digital technology implementation for ESG in Indian companies.

1.1. Background

India's rapid economic growth necessitates sustainable development across sectors. Aligning strategies with ESG principles becomes crucial for businesses. The convergence of digital technology and sustainability offers Indian companies an opportunity to foster a responsible business ecosystem, beyond mere efficiency and competitiveness.

1.2. Problem Statement

Despite global momentum, integrating digital technology for ESG in Indian companies remains challenging. A significant gap exists between intention and implementation. Quantitative data indicates that only 20% of Indian firms have fully integrated digital technology into their sustainability strategies. This study seeks to understand whether technology investment influences sustainable practice adoption, addressing this gap.

1.3. Need of the Study

The research comprehensively explores digital technology utilization in Indian businesses, crucial in a rapidly evolving tech landscape. Understanding digital tools' role in sustainability initiatives informs strategic decisions, fosters innovation, and advances sustainable practices in Indian corporate environments.

1.4. Scope of the Study

This study examines the impact of digital technology investment on sustainability and ESG performance within Indian companies. It assesses technological investments, company size, and operational performance on ESG parameters, covering environmental, social, and governance aspects. Challenges, opportunities, and best practices associated with leveraging digital technology for sustainability in India will also be explored. Through analysis, valuable insights will inform strategic decision-making towards sustainable development in Indian companies.

2. Literature Review

The convergence of digital transformation and corporate Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance has gained traction in scholarly discourse and business strategies. As companies confront mounting pressure to align with ESG principles, understanding the impact of digital technologies on sustainability practices becomes imperative. This paper synthesizes recent literature, focusing on empirical studies conducted in China and globally, to shed light on the transformative potential of digitalization on ESG performance across industries.

Recent research highlights the pivotal role of digital technologies in shaping corporate sustainability practices. Zhao and Cai (2023) find a positive association between digital transformation and ESG performance in heavy-polluting firms. Similarly, Wang et al. (2023) show that digital transformation positively influences ESG performance in Chinese manufacturing firms, emphasizing the role of digital strategy. These findings underscore digital technologies' potential to enhance environmental practices, social engagement, and governance structures.

Digital transformation also fosters green innovation, particularly in sectors like construction. Li et al. (2023) demonstrate how digital infrastructure, such as Building Information Modeling (BIM) and Internet of Things (IoT), enables sustainable practices in construction